

THE IDEOLOGICAL DEPORTATION OF FOREIGNERS AND “LOCAL SUBJECTS OF FOREIGN EXTRACTION” IN INTERWAR EGYPT

By Rim Naguib

On 23 July 1924, the Egyptian police arrested the Alexandrian Jewish syndicalist, Youssef Rosenthal, brought him to a detention facility in Kum al-Dikka, and told him that he was to be expelled from the country. His protestations of being an Egyptian citizen were ignored. Rosenthal was put on board the *Thimsis*—a cargo vessel—with a document allowing him to disembark in Romania, where he had no relatives and feared for his safety as a Jew. Upon arrival, Romanian authorities did not permit him to disembark, and attempts to deliver him in various other ports also failed. A month later, Rosenthal returned to Alexandria aboard the same cargo vessel, only to find the Egyptian police waiting at the port to prevent him from disembarking. The ship’s captain, dismayed at being embroiled in the affair, refused to depart until the deportee left the ship. Stuck aboard the *Thimsis*, Rosenthal managed to escape for a short time until the police captured him and returned him to the vessel. Weeks passed while the Egyptian government tried in vain to get rid of him. He was finally allowed to remain in Egypt on the condition that he would refrain from political and labor activism.¹

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The authorities were also planning to deport Sakellaris Yannakakis, a well-known sponge trader in Alexandria who had helped establish the Egyptian Socialist Party with Rosenthal in 1921. Yannakakis was arrested along the other leaders and members of the party in 1924. The Italian consulate intervened to prevent his trial in a local court and arrange his repatriation, since Yannakakis's parents had migrated to Egypt from Kalymnos, which was under Italian rule at the time of his arrest.² Yannakakis refused Italian "protection" and claimed local subject status because his Greek parents had come to Egypt when Kalymnos was part of Ottoman territory, which rendered them Ottoman subjects. Failing to sort out the confusion over his nationality, the government imprisoned Yannakakis with the indigenous Socialist Party leaders.³

At first glance, these deportation attempts may seem like manifestations of soaring nationalist sentiments following the popular mobilizations for Egyptian independence in 1919. Indeed, they occurred within a few months of the nationalist Wafd party's sweeping victory in the first legislative elections in the country's history under the first Egyptian constitution. These national milestones followed the 28 February 1922 Unilateral Declaration of Egypt's Independence, ushering in various measures of "Egyptianization" of state and economy.⁴

Yet an examination of interwar correspondence among the Ministry of Interior's European Department, the British Residency, and the Foreign Office reveals that these deportations were in fact the culmination of a British policy to remove socialists and internationalists from London's Egyptian semicolony and stem the revolutionary tide of the spring of 1919.⁵ British authorities had long considered and desired deportations, but the colonial administration was reluctant to pursue them in the absence of incriminating evidence for fear of stirring objections or questioning in the metropole. Following Egypt's formal independence, British officials endeavored to institute the practice—through their control over the Department of Public Security via the British-run European Department—using the façade of Egyptian sovereignty.⁶ They resorted to the physical removal of socialists, communists, trade unionists, and their families from Egypt despite their legal status as local subjects, or in the absence of proof that they were subjects of another state, rendering them stateless or expelling them to unknown destinations.⁷

This article examines these deportations as an example of the “colonial rule of difference.”⁸ Deportations were part of a colonial governmentality that violated metropolitan liberal and civic principles and reinforced a duality in the definition of rights between the metropole and the colonized society. Because many of the deportees were Ottoman subjects who—based on a 1900 decree—were entitled to legal local subject status, the deportations were based on ethnic difference.⁹ I hence describe these deportations as *ideological-ethnic*.

Ideological-ethnic deportations diverged from older practices of criminal deportations or British subjects’ repatriations in important ways. The British colonial administration neither proved that the deportees were subjects of another state for repatriation, nor accused them of a crime for which they had to stand trial under their country’s jurisdiction. Rather, following the Russian Revolution of 1917 and the emergence and activity of mixed labor unions in Egypt after World War I, the administration started deporting suspected “Bolsheviks” to the USSR or to whatever European country they were believed to have originated from. These deportations proceeded without adequate evidence of nationality or “origin,” but through assumptions of ethnic belonging and ideological association. This new form of ideological-ethnic deportation required its own legitimating mechanisms since it contradicted international laws and practices, civic principles upheld in the British metropole, and the proclaimed colonial mission of protecting foreigners and minorities residing in Egypt.

The colonial practice of ideological-ethnic deportation provided important precedents and was integrated into the laws and practices of the Egyptian postcolonial state. I examine interwar government directives to regulate the entry and presence of refugees and migrants of the defunct Ottoman Empire in Egypt—particularly certain ethnic groups perceived to be carriers of socialist ideologies—as well as antisocialist legislation. The process and timing of this legislation demonstrate how the practice of colonial exceptionalism became integrated into Egyptian state laws and institutions at a critical moment of transition toward political independence and nation-state building. I highlight the role British officials and advisers played in the legitimation of deportation, selective naturalization, and denaturalization based on ethnicity and ideology.

I also survey public discourse in *al-Ahram* during the mid-1920s.¹⁰ In the newspaper's coverage of the deportations that followed the crackdown on the Communist Party and the associated workers' confederation in 1924, *al-Ahram's* Alexandria correspondent addressed the nation and national institutions and recommended policies for the assertion of national sovereignty.¹¹ Most significantly, *al-Ahram* linked ethnicity, nationality, and ideology by constructing socialism, communism, and labor activism as a foreign epidemic and depicted the large number of foreigners living and arriving in Alexandria as a threat to national security and sovereignty. I propose that the colonial recourse to deportations reinforced the ethnic character of postcolonial Egyptian nationalism.

This is not to argue that ethnic formulations of Egyptian nationhood were nonexistent prior to this colonial practice. Certainly, colonialism had long maintained racial and ethnic hierarchies, and extraterritorial rights enjoyed by European residents reinforced the demarcation between indigenous and foreign population. Nor does this article interpret the rise of Egyptian ethnonationalism as directly caused by this particular form of colonial policing. In the global interwar context of the disintegration of multinational empires and the universalization of national states, claims for self-determination were linked to ethnic constructions. In Egypt too, Ottoman subjects were increasingly delineated as "foreigners" despite their legal status as "local subjects" under the jurisdiction of local courts, even while the country remained legally a province of the Ottoman Empire.¹²

Until 1929, however, no ratified law defined Egyptian nationality in ethnic terms.¹³ The protracted formulation of the first Egyptian nationality law coincided with the peak of ethnic-ideological deportations. The timing was not inconsequential. The colonial practice reinforced the definition of Egyptian nationality and nationhood in ethnic and religious terms and became entrenched in Egyptian state laws and practices, as well as in public discourse on Egyptian sovereignty, throughout the following decades.

Scholars of colonialism have recently begun examining the deportation of criminals and undesirable white colonial settlers from British colonies and dominions.¹⁴ But ideological-ethnic deportation from the colonies, as colonial practice, is yet to be a focus of colonial history.¹⁵ This intervention challenges an established colonial narrative that attributes postcolonial expulsions of ethnic minorities to a supposedly inherent xenophobia in

anticolonial nationalism. Instead, it highlights the role of colonial policies in postcolonial ethnonationalist practices.

Filtering Migrant Residents in the Semicolony

From the mid-nineteenth century to World War I, Egypt became deeply integrated into the world economy as a cotton exporter, and consequently highly dependent on European finance and trade. European and Levantine businessmen, bankers, brokers, and merchants dominated a wide range of financial and legal services that emerged in Alexandria, Cairo, and the Suez Canal cities to cater to Egypt's international trade.¹⁶ At the same time, the thriving colonial economy attracted large numbers of subsistence workers and artisans from Europe and the Eastern Mediterranean, turning Egypt's urban centers—especially Alexandria—into colonial cities with significant proportions of migrant residents. By the time Britain occupied Egypt in 1882, Europeans and Levantines constituted roughly a quarter of Alexandria's population and eight percent of Cairo's, a proportion which would continue to grow in the following decades until the 1930s.¹⁷

European nationals, subjects, and protégés residing in Egypt were exempt from local jurisdiction, tax, conscription, and police searches throughout the period in question by virtue of the capitulatory privileges that Ottoman sultans had granted European states between the sixteenth and nineteenth century. The capitulations binding the Egyptian province/state survived the Ottoman Empire and were not completely abolished in Egypt until 1949. Accordingly, consular courts had the exclusive right to look into criminal suits filed against their own subjects, creating a plurality of jurisdictions.¹⁸

European consulates regularly deported convicts from Egypt; these were sent to serve their sentences in the country of which they were subject, or the colony from which they originated, and often banned from returning to Egypt. Each consulate, especially the British, systematically filtered out “undesirables” from among its nationals and subjects, including men running brothels “living off the proceeds of prostitutes,” women sex workers, and “distressed” subjects descending into vagrancy, drug or alcohol abuse, and “lunacy.”¹⁹ Their regular removal was designed to rid the European com-

munity in Egypt of those engaged in undesirable behavior and practices for the purpose of maintaining colonial hierarchies.²⁰

Anarchists received the same treatment at the hand of European states, especially members of the Italian anarchist movement, which thrived in the second half of the nineteenth century.²¹ European powers tried to coordinate an international policing system to control their mobility across borders and ensure their extradition once caught overseas.²² Because Alexandria was the temporary or permanent destination of many Italian anarchists, consular courts routinely deported them from Egypt throughout the latter decades of the nineteenth century.²³ Such ideological deportations, however, still functioned in the same way as criminal transfers, and were justified by the requirements of the capitulations. The concerned consulate initiated and carried them out with the help of local police after drawing up an accusation against certain individuals, usually of plotting to commit a violent crime.²⁴

Colonial Exceptionalism: Extraditions by Consular Order

In the metropole, Britain maintained a policy of hosting dissidents and revolutionaries and refusing extraditions based on political crimes. Up to 1905, no refugee or migrant was denied entry into Britain nor deported from the metropole.²⁵ When the Alien Act was promulgated in 1905 to control the entry of paupers from Eastern Europe, it contained an asylum provision permitting entry into the United Kingdom for those at risk of persecution or prosecution for political or religious reasons.²⁶ Moreover, Britain refused to cooperate with other European states when requested to surrender European political refugees or to bar them entry. In fact, the metropole hosted a growing number of Italian anarchists due to a British tradition of hospitality to Italian political refugees that dated from the beginning of the *Risorgimento* in the 1820s.²⁷ British authorities were also reluctant to participate in any international endeavor that would limit freedom of expression and association at home.²⁸ As a result, Britain was frequently criticized for giving refuge to foreign revolutionaries.²⁹ Many European revolutionaries inferred that British-occupied Egypt would be a safe sanctuary. But the situation in the semicolony proved exceptional.

In the first decade of the twentieth century, Alexandria was the refuge and center of activity for Russian anarcho-syndicalists, particularly members

of the Black Sea Sailors' Union Abroad.³⁰ In 1907, and again in 1913, the Russian ambassador, Alexi Smirnov, asked Egyptian police to arrest key organizers in the sailors' union and deport them to Russia for crimes that the embassy alleged they were planning to commit. Evidence was lacking, and the British-controlled Egyptian police helped plant agents provocateurs and informers among the labor organizers.³¹ This cooperation led to two prominent instances of arrest and extradition, which caused an uproar in both Egypt and Britain. Protests against the deportations erupted in Alexandria and Cairo in 1907,³² and the 1913 extradition aroused parliamentary inquiries in Britain.³³

In both cases, colonial officials unanimously defended the extradition of Russian syndicalists. They argued that the Egyptian government was powerless in the face of the legal obligations stipulated by the capitulations. Lord Cromer, the former consul-general of Egypt, and Minister of Foreign Affairs Edward Grey further argued that under the capitulations a crime need not have been committed for a consulate's request to be put into effect.³⁴ Most importantly, British officials proclaimed that colonial territories were an exception to the international obligation of providing asylum to political refugees. In Cromer's words: "a country which is not indeed British territory, but which is held by a British garrison and in which British influence is predominant affords no safe asylum for a political refugee."³⁵

This exception to the principle of granting political asylum likely stemmed, not from the colonial administration's desire to abide by the capitulations (which the same British officials had staunchly criticized), but from its fear of the influence of radical, anti-authoritarian, and socialist ideas among Egyptians. It was around this time, particularly in 1908 and 1911, that indigenous workers emerged for the first time as independent labor organizers. They staged important strikes in the Cairo Tramway Company, which were characterized by remarkable unity among tramway workers despite their different nationalities and large numbers.³⁶ The police intervened in the company's favor, as the British feared that labor activism among indigenous workers might turn into nationalist agitation.³⁷ For the British administration, the presence of Russian anarcho-syndicalists in the semicolony threatened to radicalize the population. In January 1913, the chief of the Alexandria police reportedly told Ambassador Smirnov that he was amazed at the speed with which anarchist teachings were spreading and taking root in Egypt.³⁸

The capitulations thus allowed Britain a legal cover for the ideological deportation of Europeans whose presence was undesirable in the semicolon. The exception of colonial territories from the prerogatives of providing sanctuary, or from the civic principles that protected individuals from deportation based on ideology or ethnicity, was intrinsic to British colonialism's preoccupation with ensuring the docility and isolation of the colonized population.

Fighting “Bolshevism” Through Deportation: Dilemmas of Legitimation

Prewar syndicalism in Egypt was almost exclusively the domain of Italian, Greek, and Russian workers, and had limited influence on Egyptian labor.³⁹ Following World War I, however, indigenous workers constituted a growing proportion of the proletariat. They experienced inflation, dismissals, and wage cuts following the war, and initiated a wave of labor mobilizations in late 1918 through the spring of 1919. Egyptian workers formed unions and went on strike at the railway companies in Cairo and Alexandria, at the Cairo Tramway Company, the Suez Canal Company, and several others. The nationalist political elite and the press treated the strike wave of 1919 as an integral part of the national struggle against foreign domination.⁴⁰ At the same time, the mobilization of indigenous labor encouraged foreign workers and syndicalists to form mixed unions that emphasized unity across ethnic and occupational lines.⁴¹

New prospects for joint activism between indigenous and European workers and syndicalists aroused British fears of the spread of “Bolshevism” in Egypt. British intelligence turned their attention to what they described as “foreign Bolshevik agents” as a major threat to colonial interests. Thus began a systematic policy of deporting syndicalist, socialist, and communist foreigners. Before the mass mobilizations of 1919, consulates eager to pursue dissidents taking refuge in the British semicolon made deportation requests from the Egyptian police. In the aftermath of 1919, the British administration started to initiate political deportations from Egypt in an attempt to halt the radicalization of the indigenous population. Prior to the Declaration of Independence, deportations still had to go through the consulates of the countries of origin of the deportees and proving nationality, origin, or subject status was somewhat necessary.

When the Cairo Tramway workers' strike of 1919 spread to other companies, British intelligence pointed to "nationalists and Europeans" as culprits. They designated two Italians as conspirators: Max Di Collalto, the owner of the Italian-language Cairene daily *Roma* and leader of the Société internationale des employés du Caire, which claimed over a thousand members, and Giuseppe Pizzuto, an Italian subject born in Egypt, the president of the Printers' Union and founder of the Bourse du Travail. Pizzuto was credited with having integrated indigenous workers within the hitherto exclusively European Printers' Union.⁴²

The British Residency proposed "some strong action with regard to Pizzuto,"⁴³ namely, deportation through a British-requested Italian consular order. When the director of military intelligence, Major Courtney, communicated to the high commissioner that "the military authorities desired [Pizzuto's] immediate expulsion,"⁴⁴ he was arrested and deported by consular decree. Courtney later estimated that "the deportation of this man has had a very good effect and has considerably frightened the socialistic and Bolshevistic sets [in Egypt]."⁴⁵ As for Di Collalto, Special High Commissioner Lord Allenby requested his immediate deportation from the Italian ambassador and he was sent back to Italy.⁴⁶ Admitting that syndicalism was not a crime, the acting high commissioner, Milne Cheetham, argued however that syndicalism was "somewhat unsuited to the mentality and present development of the working classes in Egypt."⁴⁷

The British also initiated cooperation schemes with European consulates for the expulsion and prohibition from entry of other European "Bolsheviks." Discussions between the Foreign Office and the Italian Embassy in London resulted in instructions sent to consulates in Egypt to "concert measures to combat Bolshevik activities."⁴⁸ The French and Italian diplomatic agents agreed to lend the British authorities in Egypt "support in the work of pacification" through "reciprocal exchange of information" and consular deportation orders upon British request.⁴⁹

Youssef Rosenthal, the Russians, and the Greeks

In the spring of 1921, British intelligence reckoned that the situation in Egypt called for more deportations. Acting Director of Intelligence Humphrey Beaman argued that since the expulsion of Pizzuto, "Bolshevik activity and

influences have quadrupled.⁵⁰ Indeed, European socialists and communists in Alexandria including Greeks, Russians, Armenians, and Italians were beginning to form socialist and syndicalist organizations that increasingly included Egyptians. Youssef Rosenthal was a central figure in this process.

Rosenthal's descent from a family of Russian Jewish migrants to the Ottoman Empire, his own migration within Ottoman territories in the late nineteenth century, and the subsequent difficulty colonial and national authorities experienced trying to legitimate and implement his expulsion make him a relevant case through which to examine the interwar practice of ideological-ethnic deportation. His insistence on being integrated as an Egyptian in the social struggle unfolding in Egypt and to include the indigenous intelligentsia and workers in the socialist and labor organizations he helped establish demonstrates the uniqueness of internationalist profiles in an age of rising nationalisms.

Youssef was born in Safed, Palestine in 1872 to a mother who had also been born in Palestine. His father emigrated to Palestine in 1853 at the age of twelve from the Zhytomyr province of northern Ukraine to escape the twenty-five-year period of conscription imposed on Jewish boys in the Russian Empire. As a teenager, Youssef moved to Beirut, where he lived for ten years. It was there that he became acquainted with revolutionary ideas and hosted internationalist discussion groups in his jewelry shop.⁵¹ In 1899, he relocated to Alexandria for the economic opportunities it offered to a young jeweler of rising repute and for the margin of freedom and thriving internationalist milieu it promised a radical activist. At the time of his deportation in 1924, Rosenthal had thus lived his entire life in the Ottoman Empire.

Upon his arrival in Egypt, Rosenthal actively participated in Italian, Russian-Jewish, and Greek labor activism and organization.⁵² Nevertheless, he was from the outset interested in radical activity among the local population. During his early years in Egypt, while working in the jewelry workshop of a Jewish businessman, he incited the Egyptian workers to fight for better working conditions and an eight-hour workday.⁵³ When indigenous workers mobilized in 1919, Rosenthal began to act on his long-held conviction that it was possible and necessary to integrate the native working class in labor organization.⁵⁴ In 1921, he created the *Confédération générale des travailleurs (CGT)*, which united existing unions of foreign and native workers,

organized hitherto unorganized workers, and linked socialist groups with the labor movement. The CGT began by attracting a small number of workers from twenty-one unions, whose three thousand members were mostly foreign workers in Alexandria. But by 1924 its membership was estimated at fifteen to twenty thousand.⁵⁵ Rosenthal thus became “a bridge between the ‘foreign’ and ‘native’ [labor] movements.”⁵⁶

Several socialist groupings, composed mostly of Greeks, Armenians, and Russians, were active in 1920 in Alexandria. Their memberships overlapped and all had links to Youssef Rosenthal.⁵⁷ Their activities culminated in the establishment of the Egyptian Socialist Party (ESP) in 1921 by Rosenthal and his comrades, which actively recruited Egyptian left-wing intellectuals.⁵⁸ The party came to public attention when renowned members of the Egyptian intelligentsia joined the endeavor in August 1921 and *al-Ahram* published the party program.⁵⁹

As soon as the ESP was founded, British authorities began considering the deportation of “foreign” communists and socialists. But Foreign Office officials were apprehensive about the use of martial law to deport a large number of Europeans from Egypt, which they were certain would raise objections in the metropole. It was suggested then that the police and intelligence “between them, make out a case against certain persons.”⁶⁰

British intelligence focused its attention on Rosenthal. Together with the British director of public security and the Foreign Office, they contemplated at length the possibility and means to deport him from Egypt. The adviser to the Ministry of Interior wrote a special note about Rosenthal stating that as early as 1901, he “came to the notice of the police as a rabid and fanatical anarchist spreading subversive propaganda amongst the local Jews,” and that “he figured prominently in the [1913 extradition] case of Adamovitch,” as well as “reported by the refugees’ administration as being the instigator of intrigue and troubles amongst Russian Jews.” The note also mentioned his 1920 strike of the *Syndicat des locataires*, of which he was president, and his central role in the tailors’ and barbers’ employees strikes of the same year.⁶¹ The links he had with various socialist groups and labor organizations impressed them, to the extent that they believed the deportation of one man would seriously affect the prospects of radicalization in the country. One correspondence argued that “communism in Egypt was a one-man show and that the one man is Rosenthal.”⁶²

Correspondences between the Residency and the Foreign Office noted Rosenthal's "established position in Alexandria" and his connections with foreign journalists, such as the assistant editor of *The Egyptian Gazette*, adding: "It is possible that persons like her might try and raise dust in England if Rosenthal was deported, and we should therefore require a good case against him before taking any such action in order to have a complete answer on any inquiries that might be made."⁶³ "G. C." from the War Office wrote back to the director of public security in the Ministry of Interior citing the benefits of deporting Rosenthal, but expressed his concern that "Rosenthal seems to have remained within the law. . . . There may therefore be some outcry unless he is sent away quietly."⁶⁴

The Residency thus chose to wait until an accusation could be made against Rosenthal that would legitimize his deportation. When a large number of copies of a circular in Italian was intercepted in the mail from Vienna, signed "Partito Comunista Egiziano," British officials found it a good opportunity to deport Rosenthal. The circular commented on the ethnic strife in Alexandria which took place in May 1921, calling it "a tragic instance of racial hatred" that should not mislead the people into ignoring the source of evil: capitalism and British imperialism. It called upon indigenous and European workers to struggle together within their common worker unions for their "moral and material interests" and against "racial hatred, religious and patriotic fanaticism, inequality, and social injustice."⁶⁵ When Rosenthal was suspected as the intended recipient of the bundles of the "inflammatory" circular, British intelligence deemed that,

this is a definite case establishing Mr. Rosenthal as agent here for Bolshevik and communist associations in Europe. He is attempting to introduce surreptitiously subversive literature written especially for Egypt and certain to foment trouble and disturb public security. It seems enough to warrant action on the part of the Egyptian government, or by us under martial law, and his removal might leave the growing communist party in this country without an organizing lead.⁶⁶

But the Department of Public Security could not establish that Rosenthal was the receiver of the circular copies, and alternatively sought to justify a deportation to Russia based solely on proof of his alleged Russian nationality. Until then, the Special Section assumed that Rosenthal was Russian.⁶⁷ When

it was discovered that he was a local subject, British intelligence sought again to make out a case against him.⁶⁸ But Rosenthal had not broken any laws. The attempt to remove him from Egypt reached a temporary standstill, until an opportunity arose from the declaration of February 1922 and its repercussions. The new, albeit nominal, Egyptian state sovereignty offered a façade behind which to hide British responsibility in Rosenthal's deportation.

Considerations of deporting Rosenthal were part of a larger scheme to deport all foreign communists and syndicalists, which became more important to British policy beginning in 1921. An intelligence report argued:

It seems to be more or less accepted that sooner or later strong measures will have to be taken, and I cannot see the advantage of deferring their adoption. . . . It is easier to deport a few leaders today and deal with the still embryonic organizations than it will be when the disciples have multiplied by hundreds and the bonds are strengthened between Bolsheviks abroad and all the discontented and revolutionary elements in Egypt.⁶⁹

The Foreign Office responded that they needed to "make out a case against certain persons," adding "anything in the nature of indiscriminate deportations would probably land us in difficulties."⁷⁰ Subsequent reports named "definite persons": those they perceived to be "aiming at affiliating the Egyptian nationalist party to the Third International," such as Ben Zion Pasvolsky, an employee of the Maspero cigarette factory, or Rosenberg, a Russian who was observed speaking at the labor meeting in Jardin de Rosette on May Day. Later, the name of Zaidman came up.⁷¹ Commenting on the Special Section's report, the Foreign Office remarked that Zaidman "may shortly give the Egyptian government an excuse to deport him."⁷²

Concerns over Bolshevik propaganda raised suspicions over Russians in general, and pointed to the large number of Russian refugees, especially at the Sidi Bishr camp set up by the British. In his correspondence with the Foreign Office, the inspector of Russian refugees warned that "a considerable amount of Bolshevik propaganda is going on in this camp."⁷³ Already in 1920, the British and Egyptian authorities were coming to a consensus that the presence of Russian refugees in Egypt was dangerous and undesirable. Allenby reported to the British foreign secretary, Earl Curzon, that the Egyptian prime minister had expressed great concern about the danger of

Bolshevism being introduced by Russian refugees, and strongly urged the removal of this threat from Egypt immediately.⁷⁴ Curzon replied, “There seems to be no reason why any Russians who give trouble should not be sent back to Russia.”⁷⁵

Beside the Russians, Alexandria police closely monitored the Greeks who had been active in various socialist discussion groups. They drafted regular reports on “the activities of the branch of the Third International in Alexandria,” which was the mostly Greek Groupe d’Études Sociales and the Clarté group (associated with the French communist antinationalist Clarté), whose activities were reported to have shifted from “purely academical” to avowedly communist. Reports alleged they were “propagand[ing] [*sic*] communist ideas both verbally and by books amongst people outside the Club.”⁷⁶ Sakellaris Yannakakis was a member of these groups before he became a founder of the ESP.⁷⁷ Iordanis Iordanidis, another leading member, was a teacher at the Victoria College of Alexandria. He was reportedly teaching Bolshevik ideas in his chemistry class, and, in the summer of 1921, was refused a reentry visa to Egypt after a trip to Greece.⁷⁸

A Convergence of Colonial and “National Interests”

The revival of labor activism in 1923 reignited British fears of Bolshevism. The CGT, which was by now closely linked to the renamed Egyptian Communist Party (ECP), played a key role in one of the first and largest strikes of 1923: the February Alexandria Gas and Electric workers’ strike.⁷⁹ The following month, the CGT planned a demonstration against the Labor Conciliation Board—a government board formed in 1919 to mediate between workers and employers—accusing it of serving the interests of employers at the expense of workers. To prevent the demonstration, the authorities arrested the leaders of the ECP and CGT, Husni al-‘Urabi, and Antoine Maroun, raided and shut down the party’s headquarters, and seized its documents.⁸⁰ It was Alexander Keown-Boyd, the director general of the European Department in the Ministry of Interior, who ordered the crackdown. Two years later, he wrote to the Foreign Office, “so serious did the movement become that I had Husny el Araby [*sic*] and Antoun Maroun arrested . . . and they were sent for trial by military court.” He complained, however, that “unfortunately this court, imbued with the British idea that all persons are at liberty to express

their opinions and that you cannot do anything to them for such opinions until they convert them to direct action, acquitted these gentlemen.”⁸¹

Reference to the multi-ethnic character of the members of the ECP and CGT was central in British reports on the labor mobilizations of the spring of 1923, which singled out foreigners and accused them of orchestrating the strikes: “it would appear that the individuals principally concerned in [stirring up the railway employees] are Italians and Romanians.”⁸² However, no deportation of Europeans occurred in the aftermath of these strikes.

Following the abolition of martial law and the formation of “the government of the people” by the Wafd, the long-contemplated deportations would finally materialize.⁸³ By January 1924, the British authorities’ need to legitimize the deportations—through proof of crime or national origin—dampened, and more drastic extrajudicial measures would ensue.

The recourse to deportations that year appeared all the more urgent for the British following an intense wave of labor mobilizations from November 1923 to March 1924, culminating in workers’ occupation of the National Textile and the Egolín Oil factories in Alexandria. In this wave of worker mobilizations, the CGT played an important role, particularly in the Egolín Factory strike and occupation. The strikes coincided with the electoral victory of the Wafd, which made its charismatic leader, Sa’d Zaghlul, Egyptian premier. In contrast with the widespread sympathy with the strike wave of 1919, nationalist discourse grew hostile to the workers’ movement, as the political leadership now perceived it as a campaign to discredit the Wafd government and the nationalist cause of independence.

On 23 February 1924, Sa’d Zaghlul decided to end the occupation of the factories. He ordered the under-secretary of state, ‘Ali Gamal al-Din Pasha, and Keown-Boyd to proceed to Alexandria with a battalion of Egyptian infantry and instructed them “to show a firm front.” The Ministry of Interior’s delegation reported that the strikes were “the work of agitators” rather than stemming from real grievances, and “engineered by the communist party.”⁸⁴

Antoine Maroun, a lawyer of Levantine descent and a native of Alexandria, was singled out as a main agitator. Keown-Boyd’s reports stressed his foreignness, describing him as someone “who came from outside and displaced the men’s own Egyptian representatives.”⁸⁵ The pro-British *Egyptian Gazette* even emphasized that Maroun was not a Muslim, asking

with suspicion “how a Maronite from Mount Lebanon came to be the leader of Egyptian Moslem working men,” and advancing that he was acting with opportunistic motives.⁸⁶ Keown-Boyd’s report also emphasized the striking workers’ foreignness, stating that “large numbers of the employees are Russians, Poles, Jews, etc.” and attributed responsibility for the events to them, especially the Russian Jews. Two of the Russian Jews, Katz and Zandberg, were among ninety workers whom the company planned to dismiss.⁸⁷ Keown-Boyd described them as “moving spirits of trouble and in [Maroun’s] hands,” adding, “it is hoped that [the striking workers] may all, at least those of foreign origin, be sent out of the country.”⁸⁸

In addition to Keown-Boyd’s emphasis on Maroun’s and the Russian Jewish workers’ foreignness and non-Islamic faith, the Residency highlighted the national origin and faith of the owner of the oil factory where the strike was taking place. They pointed out that Egolín was owned by a Russian Jew called Ilia Paenson and financed by Banco di Roma. The Residency even considered asking Banco Di Roma to stop financing Egolín, for the “preponderating Russian element in this company.”⁸⁹

The Wafdist government began its term by outlawing the ECP, arresting its members and suspected sympathizers, and shutting down the CGT.⁹⁰ The court pronounced seven of the leaders guilty of inciting workers to commit criminal acts and spreading “revolutionary ideas contradicting the principles of the constitution.”⁹¹ Most were handed three-year prison sentences. A year later, Antoine Maroun died in prison while on hunger strike to protest the conditions of his incarceration.

Considering the social composition of its leadership, the Wafd’s campaign against communists and syndicalists was to be expected. Many in the party’s high command were large landowners who saw their interests threatened by the ECP’s social justice program, particularly its advocacy of land redistribution.⁹² The prosecution brought up this particular clause in the party program during the trial as evidence of the ECP’s attempt to “change the fundamental institutions of society” in violation of the Egyptian constitution of 1923.⁹³ The Wafd was also acting on its need to refute British accusations of being in “alliance with international communism,” which British intelligence leveled against it to discredit it.⁹⁴ It even felt compelled to distance itself from the milder social democracy of the British Labor Party and to insist on its nonideological nature.⁹⁵

From a different angle, the Wafd as a national liberation movement was bound to seek the fulfillment of colonial interests.⁹⁶ In its efforts to convince Britain that Egypt was capable and deserving of full independence and national sovereignty, the Wafd embarked on reappropriating British fears of “Bolshevism” in the semicolon. Once in government, the party’s policy and discourse reproduced colonial exceptionalism, by deeming freedom of expression and association, socialism, and syndicalism essentially unsuitable for Egypt and Egyptians.

Even with the Wafd out of power, the government campaign against leftists continued unabated.⁹⁷ The whole of Egypt’s political elite now shared the colonial aversion to leftist ideologies as inimical to the Egyptian state and social order.⁹⁸ This was due in part to the political dominance of large landowners throughout the period in question and the emergence of a “local bourgeoisie.” Together with the intelligentsia, the local bourgeoisie propounded ideas of economic nationalism that demanded productivity from Egyptian workers to achieve economic independence regardless of low pay and poor working conditions.⁹⁹ Nevertheless, another important factor was the impact of colonial policy on state institutions and public discourse. As British officials singled out foreigners as Bolsheviks threatening public security, so, too, did the press and nationalist government associate leftist ideologies with foreigners, depicting them as threats to the social order and national sovereignty.

British officials commended the Wafd government on its crackdown and encouraged the deportation of foreign communists and the development of anticommunist propaganda on religious grounds. Keown-Boyd reassured the Residency and Foreign Office:

Saad Pasha informed me that he intended . . . to deal with the various Russians and others concerned by having them deported from Egypt. He was thinking out means of dealing with communists of Egyptian nationality, and thought that parliament would not find it difficult to deal with communism on the grounds of its being opposed to the principles of the Mohamedan religion.¹⁰⁰

Allenby wrote to London, “the authorities are showing commendable energy and determination in dealing with the situation,” and “there is every indication that the government is determined to institute measures to prevent the

spread of communist propaganda in Egypt.”¹⁰¹ British colonial and Egyptian nationalist policy and discourse thus converged on the dangers of socialism in Egypt and the foreignness of its proponents.

“The Wandering Communist”

On 20 March 1924, *al-Ahram* reported that preparations were underway “to deport those communists whose involvement in the crimes committed by the accused was not proven. These are known Russians and Syrians.” In their case, deportation was not a verdict based on a specific crime, but a preventive measure, based on their ideology and ethnicity, against the perceived threat they posed. From that point onward, the government arrested and deported many Russians, Palestinian Jews, Greeks, Armenians, and Italians whom it suspected of communist activities or beliefs, notwithstanding their status as local or former Ottoman subjects, and despite their possessing no other nationality documentation.

Although Rosenthal was one of the ESP’s main founders, he had been dismissed from the ECP at the end of 1922 due to internal personal rivalries, and was therefore not among the accused when its leadership was prosecuted.¹⁰² Instead, the parquet summoned Rosenthal as a witness. At court, he answered the parquet’s questions without overtly identifying himself as a communist. *Al-Ahram* published the full transcript of the interrogation.¹⁰³ But two days later, Rosenthal felt compelled to send a personal statement to the newspaper. In the statement, he proclaimed: “I have been and I still am and I will always be, until the last breath, a communist wholly loyal to the cause of the proletariat” and asked for his “share of responsibility,” that is, to be detained and tried along his Egyptian comrades.¹⁰⁴

A few days later, the parquet summoned Rosenthal again and questioned him over the published statement. Rosenthal confirmed the views he expressed in the letter and was consequently arrested.¹⁰⁵ The Ministry of Interior ordered his deportation from Egypt “because of his communist inclination.”¹⁰⁶ Accompanying Rosenthal on the same cargo ship were two Russian Jews and members of the ECP: Samuel Zaslavsky and Grigorii Schoklender. However, the three of them were prohibited from disembarking at several ports, and *al-Ahram* continued to follow the whereabouts of Rosenthal under the heading “The Wandering Communist.”¹⁰⁷

With the Wafd in power and public opinion turned against foreign Bolshevik plots, British officials in Egypt felt no need to legitimate deportations through proof of origin or law infringement. Richard Graves, the acting director general of Public Security, confirmed that Rosenthal's local subject status "would not legally stand in the way of his deportation."¹⁰⁸ The Egyptian parquet's statements also made it clear that requiring proof of crimes for the deportation of foreigners with communist inclinations was redundant.¹⁰⁹

Back in Alexandria after a month on the ship, Rosenthal endeavored to prove his Egyptian nationality and to seek the protection of the 1923 constitution, arguing that he arrived in Egypt "when traveling from Palestine to Egypt was considered a domestic journey, in one Ottoman homeland."¹¹⁰

Because the authorities were unable to obtain permission from any country to receive Rosenthal, their plan to deport him failed. But they succeeded in deporting Zaslasky and Schoklender, despite family pleas published in *al-Ahram*. The parents of Grigorii Schoklender affirmed in their plea that they had moved to Alexandria fifteen years earlier, when their son was only three years old, and that he had become the breadwinner of the family.¹¹¹ Neither Schoklender nor Zaslavsky had a Russian passport. British communists aided them in obtaining Russian visas from the Russian embassy in London.¹¹² After several months in jail, Grigorii Schoklender, his family, and Samuel Zaslavsky were deported to Odessa.¹¹³ Other workers and party members described in *al-Ahram* as "Russian" or "of Russian origin" were tried in a local court and either jailed or deported.¹¹⁴

British officials in Egypt and *al-Ahram* reporters praised the Wafd government for undertaking the deportation of foreign communists and labor activists. Yet it was British authorities within the Egyptian Ministry of Interior who played a central role in deciding and implementing the deportations. The Unilateral Declaration of Independence reserved British control over four matters, including "the protection of foreign interests in Egypt and the protection of minorities." To fulfill this task, and after the elimination of the British interior adviser position, the British director general of public security was granted broad authority over the police and even controlled a special intelligence section. Keown-Boyd, director general of the European Department, held this position throughout the fourteen years of its existence from 1923 to 1937.¹¹⁵ In this period, Keown-Boyd sought to strengthen

the European Department in order to maintain a bastion of British control over Egyptian affairs.¹¹⁶ Thus, despite the creation of a new position for an Egyptian director general of public security during the Egyptianization of the state apparatus in 1922, the British administration retained control over the Egyptian police, and especially the political police.¹¹⁷

The European Department led the campaign to suppress socialism and communism in Egypt through heavy recourse to ideological deportation, while concealing British responsibility by working under the guise of Egyptian state sovereignty. A 1929 report on communism by Major Anson of the European Department stated that in the preceding six years, from 1923 to 1929, "eighty-six dangerous communists had been deported from Egypt."¹¹⁸

Deportation by administrative order occurred with very limited evidence. When the European Department uncovered a renewed attempt to form communist organizations in 1925, the police arrested all those involved in Cairo and Alexandria, including Yannakakis once again. Keown-Boyd wrote, "the case against these gentlemen is not overstrong, but we hope to get convictions." He described one organization as "Russian and Jew" and remarked that its members "possess few documents."¹¹⁹ Despite the lack of evidence, the Department of Public Security deported thirteen members of the suspected group, searched the houses of five members, and banned two individuals from returning to Egypt.¹²⁰ A few months later, twenty-two Russian Jews, five Italians, a Syrian, a Pole, and a Romanian suspected of communism were arrested and detained pending deportation.¹²¹ In another instance in 1931, eight Armenians suspected of communism and their families were put on a Soviet steamer to Odessa. In their case, the mere possession of Armenian socialist newspapers published in Paris and Athens was incriminating evidence.¹²² Deportations were decided upon in haste and executed en masse. Suspects were put on Soviet ships calling at Egyptian ports by force, and captains were prohibited from landing their cargo if they refused to take those without proper Russian documents.¹²³

While many deportees were rendered stateless, others were sent to their execution. One such case occurred in September 1925, when suspected Russian communists were deported to Odessa despite the objections of two of their number who claimed they were monarchists and veterans of the Russian White Army. Upon their arrival in Odessa, they were immediately executed. The Residency wrote to the Department of Public Security to inquire

into the issue, and Major Anson replied explaining how the deportations were decided and carried out. Graves communicated Anson's note to the Residency, agreeing that in certain cases "action was unduly precipitate." Yet he pointed to the difficulty of basing the decision on legal proof since, according to Graves, "documentary proof is rarely available" to prosecute Russians suspected of communism who do not possess Russian passports, noting the justifiable "nervousness of the Egyptian authorities with regard to the Bolshevistic propaganda."¹²⁴

Anson's note, on the other hand, implied that the process was not precipitate: the decision was a result of two meetings between police officers and members of the ministry presided over by Keown-Boyd. A "considerable amount of information was placed before them" and "each individual case for deportation was then approved in writing by both the Director General European Department [British], and the Director General Public Security Department, or [his] assistant [the latter was British]."¹²⁵ The approval of the judicial adviser of the Ministry of Interior (also British) is then obtained, after the British director of intelligence "explains the case from the point of view of passport control, and Major Anson from the point of view that these persons were politically undesirable." The British director of intelligence issued the actual deportation orders and made the necessary arrangements.¹²⁶

Anson's report demonstrates how the British European Department in the Ministry of Interior and British intelligence decided and executed these deportations as administrative orders. Yet British officials in Egypt evaded responsibility due to the dual British-Egyptian authority in place.

British officials in Egypt seemed aware of the double standards between the metropole and the semicolony and repeatedly voiced their concern about possible scandals or objections from British parliament and the press. They preferred informal over formal channels and extrajudicial over legal and judicial means. For example, in July 1925, George Lloyd, the high commissioner in Egypt, relayed to the foreign secretary an Egyptian government request for assistance for the Department of Public Security and direct communication with a comparable department in the metropole to control communist propaganda and activities. Lloyd stated in his letter to the Foreign Office that such a channel already existed "in so far as senior British officers in the Egyptian service are concerned," but that it was "undesirable to allude to this in replying to the [Egyptian government's] request."¹²⁷ The response of His

Majesty's Government to the Egyptian government was nevertheless negative, explaining that "the arrangement proposed is impracticable" because "propaganda which is dangerous in one country may be harmless in another, and the laws and practice of various states differ so profoundly that anything more than the common protection of society against criminals, as distinguished from mere advocates of extreme ideas, has proved impossible of attainment."¹²⁸

Foreigners as Threat to National Sovereignty and Public Security

Following the crackdown on the ECP, Wafdist leaders and the press attacked communists as foreign troublemakers misleading patriotic Egyptian workers. The Wafd sought to contain the tide of labor mobilization by establishing a General Union of Workers only twelve days after the arrest of the ECP leadership. The head of the Wafd's union, as well as the leaders of other unions loyal to the Wafd, engaged in an anticommunist campaign and described the 1924 strikes as the work of foreigners, jeopardizing national interests and contradicting true patriotism. *Al-Ahram* echoed this discourse; its reports and opinion pieces stressed that communism was a destructive foreign ideology, and associated its manifestation in Egypt with the presence of a large number of foreigners:

Those responsible for the violent events that the workers have carried out in the port city are the Russian refugees, and others who have taken refuge in our safe country, and are imbued with the doctrines of Lenin and his associates. No doubt the government has by now understood that these refugees are not just a burden on Egypt, but they are also a danger to its order and safety. The interest of the nation lies in cleansing Egypt of these refugees before their doctrines proliferate to an extent that will force the state to use arms to destroy them.¹²⁹

During the crackdown on the ECP and CGT, a regular section appeared on the pages of *al-Ahram* for disclaimers by workers, negating ties with communists or communism. One letter by "a labor leader" warned the workers of communism and of foreigners:

Communists are a group that convened not for the betterment of your lot but to sow the seeds of strife between you and your companies.

They are fugitives from their own countries; they destroyed their homelands. . . . They came from outside, tricked the workers, co-opted some syndicates and went about collecting the money of the workers every month with the pretext that they will serve their interests. They are cheaters and liars.¹³⁰

A week later, the reporter reassured readers that workers learned “some foreigners had instigated the strikes.”¹³¹

Simultaneously, several columns and news pieces focused on the issue of foreigners living in Egypt and the threat they allegedly posed to public security and national well-being. One such report, titled “The Foreign Gangs,” cited “police findings” to explain how certain groups of foreigners including Romanians, Greeks, and Russians were responsible for a rise in pickpocketing. It reported that some of them were “successfully deported to their countries.”¹³² Another piece titled “Foreign Thieves in Egypt” alleged the presence of a large number of foreign thieves in Alexandria and Cairo, most of whom “Russian immigrants and Greek vagrants.” The correspondent stated that “not a day passes without one of them committing a theft,” and thanked the police for its efforts “to save the country from their likes.”¹³³ He called for more border control to prevent “the vagrants and thieves” from entering Egyptian territory.

The reporter argued for the necessity to deport resident foreigners to combat these petty crimes, and associated the ability of the government to carry out such deportations with the desired assertion of national sovereignty. He complained that attempts to deport them were obstructed by the requirement that individuals should carry passports with a visa from the country to which they are to be deported, which these countries refused to grant. He exclaimed that these criminals remained in the country “against the will of its people, its government, and its police,” depriving Egypt of the right to guard its own frontiers from the intrusion of unwanted foreigners. The author further questioned the right of these residents to stay in Egypt; he criticized European consulates for refusing to issue visas “with the pretext that [those foreigners] are subjects of the local government, even while they do not know a word of Arabic!”¹³⁴

This public discourse over the need to control the entry and residence of foreigners in Egypt, especially certain ethnic groups from the now defunct

Ottoman Empire, quickly translated into government policy. In August 1924, the Ministry of Interior issued a directive on immigrants which required the registration of Russian, Turkish, Armenian, and Bulgarian immigrants. It required them to present themselves to the police in every governorate and give information about their previous occupation in their country of origin, address, and means of livelihood in Egypt, among other data. They were ordered to show their passports or entry permits to the police, and all those who failed to present themselves or provided false information were liable to deportation.¹³⁵

Al-Ahram praised the directive but considered its terms too lenient, arguing for more drastic and holistic measures for “cleansing and disinfecting” the country of those foreigners, “to avoid their evils and the crimes of chaos, war, and destruction they carry with them.” The same piece called on the government to “fight against this imported evil commodity, this deadly poison [Bolshevism], transported to us at the hands of foreigners.” It concluded that it was the duty of patriots to assist the police in monitoring foreigners who were Bolshevik propagandists in order to expel them.¹³⁶ *Al-Ahram* thus associated the issue of the presence and entry of foreigners with the threat that communism posed to Egyptian state and social order.

The Egyptian government also issued directives banning the entry of several categories of immigrants to Egypt, especially refugees. They prevented refugees fleeing the war in Hijaz from entering the country and deported a group of Turks because—as *al-Ahram* explained—“the government does not like political refugees.”¹³⁷ The Egyptian government was at ease with policies that were at odds with accepted international principles and practices, in this case the right of asylum, but which British colonial discourse and policy had defended previously as a necessary exception in the semicolony.

At the same time, an Egyptian nationality law was imminent, and one of the main issues that marked the process of its conception was the fate of former Ottoman subjects. Despite the existence of the 1900 edict determining which Ottoman subjects were entitled to Egyptian nationality—which required either a minimum length of domicile or birth in Egypt—the government was now reluctant to allow Ottoman Jews such as Rosenthal or Katz, or Ottoman Greeks like Sakellaris Yannakakis, or Christian Syrians like Antoine Maroun to be automatically naturalized as Egyptians. Indeed,

many of the internationalists the government tried to deport claimed their entitlement to stay based on the decree law of 1900.¹³⁸ During the Rosenthal deportation crisis, *al-Ahram* reported a government official declaring that “*not all* former subjects of the Ottoman empire residing in Egypt can become Egyptian.”¹³⁹ This statement led the reporter to question the fate of Ottoman subjects originating in Palestine, Syria, Lebanon, Iraq, and Hijaz living in Egypt and for whom “the resolution to the issue of Rosenthal will be a measuring stick.”¹⁴⁰ *Al-Ahram*’s correspondent was likely making the case for Muslim Ottoman subjects, as opposed to Jewish and Christian former Ottoman subjects, including Greeks, Armenians, Bulgarians, and Romanians, whom the newspaper typically depicted as the most likely carriers of socialist ideologies. This association between political opinion and ethnicity/religion would be critical in the ensuing selective naturalization of former Ottoman subjects.

Colonial Rule of Exception Inscribed into the Postcolonial Nation-state

The Nationality Law of 1929 was the culmination of a long process of deliberations by British and Egyptian jurists. Through this process, the entitlement to Egyptian nationality for Ottoman subjects who had lived in Egypt for fifteen years was omitted. The final law stipulated that a person born in Egypt to a foreign father can only be Egyptian if the father himself was born in Egypt and if he “belongs by race to the majority of the population in a country whose language is Arabic or religion is Islam.”¹⁴¹ The requirement of “belonging to the race of the majority” had been included in the Treaties of Sèvres and Lausanne in articles dealing with the fate of Ottoman subjects in Egypt. Drawing from this principle, the law accorded a special position to Arab and/or Muslim affiliation in the requirements for naturalization of former Ottoman subjects residing in Egypt.¹⁴²

The law gave extensive powers to the Ministry of Interior in approving or rejecting applications for Egyptian nationality and left the expulsion of those former Ottoman subjects who opted for another nationality wholly to the discretion of the Minister of Interior.¹⁴³ The ethnic discrimination in naturalization against non-Muslims (Jews, including indigenous ones, as well as Syrian Christians) went even further in practice following the prom-

ulgation of the law.¹⁴⁴ The naturalization of residents was thus treated—by lawmakers and in state practice—as a security issue, to be managed by the security apparatus, with marked religious-ethnic biases.

Two years after the formulation of the nationality law, the government of Isma'īl Sidqī¹⁴⁵ issued the decree-law no. 92 of 1931 as an addendum to its article 13, which provided for the loss of nationality by any Egyptian “employed by a foreign government or affiliated to revolutionary associations.”¹⁴⁶ Before the promulgation of the law, the Egyptian government presented the draft to the British authorities for advice and approval. The Residency sent a letter to Judge Booth, judicial adviser to the Ministry of Interior, which voiced the concern that the decree could “attract some attention in England.” Therefore, a copy of the law was to be sent to him in one bag and the Residency’s observations in another bag.¹⁴⁷ Booth responded by arguing that the law may create a number of stateless individuals but that “it seems hardly possible to claim that this can be said to be repugnant to legal ideas generally accepted internationally.” He curiously cited the example of the French law providing for the loss of French nationality in case of possession of or trading in slaves, which, according to Booth, was “somewhere near it.”¹⁴⁸

The European Department wrote to the Residency that the law was designed specifically to prevent the return of the Egyptian students who had gone to study at the University of the Toilers of the East in Moscow, where, according to the British head of the European section, they had “learned the principles of international agitation.”¹⁴⁹ Already in 1924, in the midst of the campaign against the ECP, the Residency was alluding to the desirability of a measure to prevent the return of the Egyptian students studying in Moscow.¹⁵⁰ Graves argued in favor of the decree because it overcame the obstacle presented by previous legislation against banishing an Egyptian subject in possession of proper nationality papers.¹⁵¹ Moreover, the European Department requested a change in the wording from “persons residing outside Egypt” to “persons outside Egypt” so as to encompass those who were abroad for shorter periods “to study Bolshevik propaganda.”¹⁵² With British support and cooperation, the law was quickly put into effect, and on 24 August 1931, the *Journal Officiel* declared eight Egyptians stripped of their Egyptian nationality, including Charlotte Rosenthal, the daughter of Youssef Rosenthal.¹⁵³

Another decree-law under consideration at the time modified articles of the criminal code in order to “facilitate action against communism.”¹⁵⁴ The proposed decree-law criminalized the formation of any organization aimed at changing the social system, even if its members did not act on its principles. It considered the mere possession of correspondence or papers relating to the activities or tendencies of such organizations to be incriminating evidence. It stipulated that any person who “encourages others to join such organizations” or “[has] knowledge of the existence of such an organization” or “shelter[s], directly or indirectly, a person guilty of this crime” was punishable.¹⁵⁵ Interestingly, the premier, Isma‘il Sidqi, first asked Keown-Boyd whether the decree-law would offend the British Labor government in power because of its strong antisocialist stance. Booth’s and Keown-Boyd’s opinions were reassuring; they both thought that the law “is not of a nature to which exception could be taken by His Majesty’s Government” but “of course they could not say that the matter might not be raised in [British] parliament.”¹⁵⁶

A Residency official described the law as “very drastic” and not justifiable by the present seriousness of the communist threat in Egypt. But he added: “it does not appear to be our business. Mustafa Kemal handles communists quite as drastically in Turkey.”¹⁵⁷ The explanatory note argued that the decree-law was needed as “it enables the authorities to effectively combat [communist] menace and to nip it in the bud,” since the existing law only criminalized the advocacy of change in the existing social system by force, intimidation, threat, or material or financial aid, whereas “there are other ways for the spread of this dangerous propaganda.”¹⁵⁸

British officials within the Egyptian state’s executive body thus actively pursued drastic anticommunist laws to legitimate exceptional means of policing. By the early 1930s, the deportation of foreigners was also an established measure of fighting communism. A “Note on Communism” prepared by Bimbashi Ahmed Mukhtar of the Special Section and approved by Major Anson enumerated five “most effective weapons against communism,” the second of which was “deportation of aliens suspected of making communist propaganda, by administrative order and not by an order from the court of law.”¹⁵⁹

Conclusion

This article examined the colonial practice of ethnic-ideological deportation in interwar Egypt, which constituted an important, yet neglected, aspect of colonial governmentality. Colonial policing relied on filtering and removing residents based on their ethnicity and ideology. Since this strategy stood in stark opposition to internationally accepted state practices and British colonialism's alleged mission of protecting foreigners and minorities, it required changing tactics of legitimation. The latter encompassed recourse to the capitulations, finding evidence of law-violation, and proving the *origin* of the person marked for deportation.

Following the February Declaration of 1922 and the ascendancy of the Wafd in government, British authorities were able to evade responsibility by recourse to the newly established, though largely nominal, sovereignty of the Egyptian state. It was then that British officials in the Egyptian Ministry of Interior carried out mass deportations by executive order and encouraged the institution and legalization of the practice. They provided legal advice to the Ministry of Interior and to successive governments and drafted explanatory notes to the Foreign Office advocating the removal of legal obstacles for ideological deportations and denaturalizations of Egyptians based on their political views.

So established was the belief that Britain's colonial mission in Egypt was to protect ethnic and religious minorities, that British commentators on the deportation of Rosenthal failed to see Britain's central role in instituting the practice of deporting non-Muslim internationalists. In her 1925 book *Britain and Egypt*, British journalist Margaret Travers Symons, assistant editor of the *Egyptian Gazette*, described the deportation of Rosenthal in a chapter titled "Can Egyptians Govern?":

The extraordinary and cruel treatment meted out to Mr. Joseph Rosenthal, a respected and well-to-do citizen of Alexandria, solely because he was a Jew, and had at one time assisted in the formation of genuine labour unions, roused considerable comment among the foreign communities, and the incident served to open the eyes of many people to the reasons why Great Britain had placed among the "reserved points" the claim to protect minorities in Egypt.¹⁶⁰

What the secret documents of the British Foreign Office and Residency reveal, and this article demonstrates, is that deportation based on ideology and ethnicity was a consistent British policy in Egypt. It was an example of the colonial rule of difference and became inscribed in nationalist discourse and in postcolonial state policies, laws, and institutions.

The findings presented here refute dominant colonialist as well as nationalist narratives. While British colonialism claimed to protect minorities and European interests in Egypt, it sought to pacify the indigenous population by physically removing undesirable European socialists and syndicalists from the semicolony, instituting the practice of uprooting families based on ethnic difference in the laws and policies of the postcolonial Egyptian state.

On the other hand, the emergent nationalist political elite in the interwar period shared similar colonial fears of a popular uprising and worked to subordinate the local population and redirect class-based movements toward conservative ethnonationalism. Ironically, the national state and its institutions adopted colonial practices and discourses of legitimation to replace colonial authorities and establish power in Egypt.

The leading national newspaper, *al-Ahram*, in turn bolstered the authorities and adopted their aims at a critical moment of nation-state building and decolonization. It addressed a growing audience aspiring to form a new independent and sovereign nation, associating communism as a destructive ideology with the entry and presence of foreigners in Egypt and constructing the issue in nationalist terms.

While British domination of public security in Egypt ended in 1937, local subjects of foreign extraction (later called *mutamassirun*, literally “Egyptianized”) were yet to be subjected to additional waves of deportation in 1949, 1951, and, more drastically, 1956. Based on this article’s propositions, it is necessary to study these as extensions of colonial practices that instituted and legitimated ethnic-ideological deportation.

ENDNOTES

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- 1 See *al-Ahram*, various issues in the period July–November 1924. *Al-Ahram*'s correspondent gave conflicting reports of Rosenthal's whereabouts during his maritime journey and the exact reason for his return to Alexandria.
- 2 The island of Kalymnos, part of the Dodecanese chain, was formally united with Greece in 1947.
- 3 See *al-Ahram*, various issues in the period September 1924–January 1925.
- 4 The declaration was issued by the British government, and stipulated that Egypt is an independent and sovereign state but reserved four realms to remain under British authority: the defense of Egypt, imperial communications, the Sudan, and the protection of foreign interests and minorities. Egyptianization measures included the abolition of British adviserships to several Egyptian ministries, and, on the economic plane, the partial Egyptianization of foreign firms as stipulated by a 1927 law.
- 5 I use “semicolon” rather than “colony” since Egypt was never legally a British colony, and its specific experience under British colonial rule was highly influenced by the retention of much of its Ottoman institutions and legal tradition. See Aimee M. Genell, “Empire by Law: Ottoman Sovereignty and the British Occupation of Egypt, 1882–1923” (PhD, Columbia University, 2013), <https://academiccommons.columbia.edu/doi/10.7916/D8J67GH7>.
- 6 The European Department was created in May 1922 within the General Directorate of Public Security, to oversee the protection of foreigners as stipulated in the February Declaration. It was empowered to intervene in all matters related to the organization and appointments of the police in Alexandria, Cairo, and the Canal Zone, and in all matters related to foreigners. For a history of the European Department, see 'Abd al-Wahhab Bakr, *Al-Bulis al-Misri, 1922-1952* [The Egyptian Police, 1922-1952], vol. 2 (Cairo: Matba'at Dar al-Kutub wa-l-Watha'iq al-Qawmiyya, 2019).
- 7 Prior to the first Egyptian nationality law of 1929, local subject status was the default status for those who did not enjoy European nationality or subject status. Local subjects included indigenous Egyptians and other subjects of the Ottoman Empire regardless of descent. See Will Hanley, *Identifying with Nationality: Europeans, Ottomans, and Egyptians in Alexandria* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2017).
- 8 See Partha Chatterjee, *The Nation and Its Fragments: Colonial and Postcolonial Histories* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1993).
- 9 The 1900 decree-law specified which Ottoman subjects were considered Egyptian: Ottomans living in Egypt for at least fifteen years, and those born in Egypt to Ottoman subjects. It became a reference that was incorporated into later legislation; see Frédéric Abécassis and Anne Le Gall-Kazazian, “L'identité au miroir du droit. Le statut des personnes en Égypte (fin XIXe - milieu XXe siècle)” [Identity in the Mirror of the Law: Personal Status in Egypt (Late 19th to Mid-20th Century)], *Égypte/Monde Arabe* 11 (1992); Will Hanley, “When did Egyptians Stop Being Ottomans? An Imperial Citizenship Case Study,” in *Multilevel Citizenship*, ed. Willem Maas (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2013), 89–109; and Shimon Shamir, “The Evolution of the Egyptian Nationality Laws and their Application to the Jews in the Monarchy Period,” in *The Jews of Egypt: A Mediterranean Society in Modern Times*, ed. Shimon Shamir (Boulder, CO: Westview Press, 1987), 37. For the 1900 edict, see *al-Waqa'i' al-Misriyya* 70, no. 74 (4 July 1900).

- 10 *Al-Ahram* remained the leading daily newspaper throughout the period in question. See Ami Ayalon, *The Press in the Arab Middle East: A History* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1995).
- 11 Following the 1919 uprising, *al-Ahram* contributed significantly in the production of national issues. For an interwar demonstrative case, see Elena Chiti, “Building a National Case in Interwar Egypt: Raya and Sakina’s Crimes through the Pages of *Al-Ahram*,” *History Compass* 18, no. 2 (February 2020).
- 12 The Egyptian censuses of 1882 and 1897 labeled Ottomans as “real” Egyptians. The 1907 census categorized them for the first time as foreigners. The census of 1917 makes further distinction between local subjects and Ottomans. Hanley, “When Did Egyptians Stop Being Ottomans?,” 97–102.
- 13 The Egyptian nationality law of 1929 instituted the criterion of being born to a father who was himself born in Egypt, “if he belongs *by race* to the majority of the population in a country whose language is Arabic or religion is Islam.” See Shamir, “The Evolution of the Egyptian Nationality Laws,” 48.
- 14 See, for example, Lauren Banko, “Keeping Out the ‘Undesirable Elements’: The Treatment of Communists, Transients, Criminals, and the Ill in Mandate Palestine,” *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History* 47, no. 6 (2019): 1153–80; Jonathan Hyslop, “Undesirable Inhabitant of the Union . . . Supplying Liquor to Natives’: D. F. Malan and the Deportation of South Africa’s British and Irish Lumpen Proletarians 1924–1933,” *Kronos* 40, no. 1 (2014): 178–97; and Jean P. Smith, “From Promising Settler to Undesirable Immigrant: The Deportation of British-Born Migrants from Mental Hospitals in Interwar Australia and South Africa,” *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History* 46, no. 3 (2018): 502–23.
- 15 Exceptions include Tapiwa B. Zimudzi, “Spies and Informers on Campus: Vetting, Surveillance, and Deportation of Expatriate University Lecturers in Colonial Zimbabwe, 1954–1963,” *Journal of Southern African Studies* 33, no. 1 (2007): 193–208.
- 16 See Sakis Gekas, “Colonial Migrants and the Making of a British Mediterranean,” *European Review of History: Revue Européenne d’histoire* 19, no. 1 (February 2012): 75–92.
- 17 Arab Republic of Egypt, Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics and Centre d’Études et de documentation économiques et juridiques, *Century Census Egypt, 1882–1996*, CD-ROM, 2003.
- 18 For a recent investigation into imperial and national state claims over subjects in colonial Alexandria, see Shana Minkin, *Imperial Bodies: Empire and Death in Alexandria, Egypt* (Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 2019).
- 19 Mak Lanver, “The British Community in Occupied Cairo, 1882–1922” (PhD diss., School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London, 2001), 173; Hanley, *Identifying with Nationality*, 227; Liat Kozma, “Women’s Migration for Prostitution in the Interwar Middle East and North Africa,” *Journal of Women’s History* 28, no. 3 (2016), 104. The Ministry of Interior contained a Lunacy Division. For examples of the deportation of lunatics, see FO 841/188/39 “Lunacy: Giuseppe Cremona” (demobilized British constable whose family resided in Egypt, deported to Malta in 1920); FO 841/197/51 “Lunacy: Charles Fairburn” (repatriated to Plymouth in 1921); FO 841/203/50 and FO 841/197/44 “Lunacy: Paolo Zarb Dalli” (deported to Malta in 1922), British National Archives (hereafter BNA).
- 20 Lanver, “The British Community,” 173; Nathan Lambert Fonder, “Pleasure, Leisure, or Vice? Public Morality in Imperial Cairo, 1882–1949” (PhD diss., Harvard University, 2013), 170; and Marios Papakyriacou, “Formulation and Definitions of the Greek National Ideology in Colonial Egypt (1856–1919)” (PhD diss., Freie Universität Berlin, 2014), 101. The justification for the deportation of British undesirables “for the sake of the prestige of the [English]

- race” was stated, for example, in Linton Thorp to the High Commissioner, 15 July 1921, CO 323/890/35, 103-105.
- 21 Nunzio Pernicone, *Italian Anarchism, 1864-1892* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2014), 133–134.
 - 22 Richard Bach Jensen, “The International Anti-Anarchist Conference of 1898 and the Origins of Interpol,” *Journal of Contemporary History* 16, no. 2 (1981): 323–47.
 - 23 See Anthony Gorman, “‘Diverse in Race, Religion and Nationality . . . But United in Aspirations of Civil Progress’: The Anarchist Movement In Egypt 1860–1940,” in *Anarchism and Syndicalism in the Colonial and Postcolonial World, 1870–1940*, ed. Lucien Walt and Steven Hirsch (Leiden: Brill, 2010), 1–32; and Anthony Gorman, “Confining Political Dissent in Egypt before 1952,” in *Policing and Prisons in the Middle East and North Africa: Formations of Coercion*, ed. Laleh Khalili and Jilian Schwedler (London: Hurst, 2010), 157–73.
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 - 25 Bernard Porter, *The Refugee Question in Mid-Victorian Politics* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1979).
 - 26 Alien Act 1905 (Stat.5 Edw. VII C.13); and Alison Bashford and Jane McAdam, “The Right to Asylum: Britain’s 1905 Aliens Act and the Evolution of Refugee Law,” *Law and History Review* 32, no. 2 (2014): 309–50.
 - 27 Pietro Di Paola, *The Knights Errant of Anarchy: London and the Italian Anarchist Diaspora (1880-1917)* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 6.
 - 28 Jensen, “The International Anti-Anarchist Conference”; and Pietro Di Paola, “The Spies Who Came in from the Heat: The International Surveillance of the Anarchists in London,” *European History Quarterly* 37, no. 2 (2007): 189–215.
 - 29 Di Paola, “The Spies Who Came in from the Heat,” 190.
 - 30 For accounts of the anarcho-syndicalist movement among the sailors of the Black Sea, see Victor Savchenko, “Anarchists and the Workers Movement of the First Quarter of the Twentieth Century in Ukraine: The Problem,” *Danubius XXXIV Supplement* (2016); and O. B. Shliakhov, “Anarxysty` ta moryaky` torgovel` nogo flotu Azovo-Chornomors`kogo base-jnu na pochatku XX st.” [Anarchists and sailors of the merchant fleet of the Azov-Black Sea Basin in the early XXth century] *Scientific and theoretical almanac «Grani»* 20; 7(147), 5-14. doi: 10.15421/171791 (in Ukrainian).
 - 31 See the correspondences of the Russian ambassador cited in G. V. Goryachkin, *al-Iskandariyya al-Rusiyya: Qadar al-Muhajirin fi Misr* (Russian Alexandria: The Fate of the Russian Emigration in Egypt), trans. ‘Ali Fahmi Abdel Salam (Cairo: al-Markaz al-Qawmi li-l-Tarjama, 2014); and Vladimir Beliakov, *Rihla ila Difaf al-Nil al-Muqaddasa: al-Rus fi Misr* [A Trip to the Sacred Shores of the Nile: The Russians in Egypt], trans. Ibrahim Anwar (Cairo: al-Markaz al-Qawmi li-l-Tarjama, 2016).
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- 37 *Ibid.*, 65.
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- 41 *Ibid.*, 119.
- 42 Major Courtney to the Chancery, 28 August 1919, FO 141/779/1, BNA, 42–45; and Milne Cheetham to Earl Curzon of Kedleston, 29 September 1919, FO 141/681/7, BNA, 18–22.
- 43 Major Courtney to the Chancery, 28 August 1919, FO 141/779/1, BNA, 57.
- 44 Milne Cheetham to Earl Curzon of Kedleston, 29 September 1919, FO 141/681/7, BNA, 21.
- 45 Major G.W. Courtney (Intelligence) to Milne Cheetham, 20 September 1919, FO 141/779/1, BNA, 78.
- 46 Major Courtney to the Chancery, 28 August 1919, FO 141/779/1, BNA, 42–45; and Milne Cheetham to Earl Curzon of Kedleston, 29 September 1919, FO 141/681/7, BNA, 18–20.
- 47 Milne Cheetham to Earl Curzon of Kedleston, 29 September 1919, FO 141/681/7, BNA, 22.
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- ‘Ummal wa-l-Ishtirakiyya fi Misr’ [Interrogations of the Communists: The Testimony of Monsieur Rosenthal. The History of the Emergence of the Workers’ and Socialist Movement in Egypt], *al-Ahram*, 7 March 1924.
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- 56 Hernández and Paonessa, “Caught Between Internationalism, Transnationalism and Immigration,” 39.
- 57 Selma Botman, *The Rise of Egyptian Communism, 1939–1970* (Syracuse, NY: Syracuse University Press, 1988), 50; and Rif’at al-Sa’id, *Tarikh al-Haraka al-Ishtirakiyya fi Misr: 1900–1925* [History of the Socialist Movement in Egypt: 1900–1925], 5th ed. (Cairo: Dar al-Thaqafa al-Jadida, 1980).
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- 61 Special Section, Public Security Department, War Office, “Note on Joseph and Charlotte Rosenthal,” 10 March 1921, FO141/779/1, BNA, 259.
- 62 Ministry of Interior, Department of Public Security, “Note on Rosenthal,” 28 September 1921, FO141/779/1, 258.
- 63 Ministry of Interior, Department of Public Security, “Note on Rosenthal,” 21 July 1921, FO141/779/1, BNA, 218.
- 64 War Office to Special Section, Ministry of Interior, 4 October 1921, FO141/779/1, BNA, 262.
- 65 G. F. Clayton to D.G.P.S, copy of intercepted circular: “Al Popolo Ingannato e Tradito” [To the Deceived and Betrayed People], 13 September 1921, FO141/779/1, BNA, 243.
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- 69 Memorandum by Hulme Beaman, “Bolshevik Activities in Egypt,” 8 July 1921, FO141/779/1 BNA, 193–195.
- 70 Minute on Residency paper No. 9065/81, 9 July 1921, FO141/779/1, BNA, 196–197.
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- 72 Public Security Department, War Office to Foreign Office (handwritten comment by FO officer), 4 October 1921, FO141/779/1, BNA, 257.
- 73 A. C. M. Paris Lieut-Colonel, Inspector Russian Refugees, Egypt to the Residency, 1 September 1921, FO141/779/1, BNA, 237.
- 74 Allenby to Curzon, Telegram 687, FO371/4992, BNA, cited in Ginat, *A History of Egyptian Communism*.
- 75 Curzon to Allenby, Telegram 661, 19 July 1920, FO371/4992, BNA, cited in Ginat, *A History of Egyptian Communism*.
- 76 Ryder, Director General of Public Security to the Residency, “Note on Recent Signs of Bolshevism,” 21 July 1921, citing report by Alexandria City Police dated 2 June 1921, FO 141/779/1, BNA, 215.

- 77 Alexander Kitroeff, "Greek Workers in Egypt, 1900–1930," *The Journal of Modern Hellenism* 3 (1986), 111.
- 78 Beaman, "Note on the Activities of the Branch of the Third International at Alexandria," 15 June 1921, FO 141/779/1, BNA, 176; and Alexandria City Police, "Groupe Clarte," 10 August 1921, FO 141/779/1, BNA, 234.
- 79 Husni al-ʿUrabi was by that time the general secretary of both the ECP and the CGT, his deputy at the CGT was a party leader, and Antoine Maroun was both CGT counselor, then CGT secretary and party deputy secretary; see Beinin and Lockman, *Workers on the Nile*, 144.
- 80 Al-Saʿid, *Tarikh al-Haraka al-Ishtirakiyya*, 272.
- 81 Keown-Boyd Director General, European Department, Ministry of the Interior to Foreign Office, "The Communist Movement in Egypt," 22 June 1925, FO141/779/1, BNA, 511.
- 82 Report by Agent, "Communism in Egypt," 4 May 1923, FO141/779/1, BNA, 331.
- 83 The Wafd's popularity cut across social classes. Its government was designated by *al-Ahram* and other papers as "the government of the people." See Marius Deeb, *Party Politics in Egypt: The Wafd and Its Rivals, 1919–1939* (Oxford: Ithaca Press, 1979).
- 84 European Department, Office of the Director General, "Note on the Strikes of the Filature Nationale and the Egyptian Oil Industries," 27 February 1924, FO141/779/1, BNA, 335–338.
- 85 Ibid., 337.
- 86 *The Egyptian Gazette*, "Communism in Egypt: History of the Movement I," 24 July 1924
- 87 Avram Katz and Hillel Zandberg were both teenagers in 1924. Katz's parents had immigrated to the Ottoman Empire when he was two years old, and Zandberg came to Egypt later as political refugee. Anticipating arrest, they sought the assistance of Italian communists to flee Egypt to the Soviet Union. They were tried in absentia along the other party leaders and given the maximum sentence. Ginat, *A History of Egyptian Communism*, 39–40, 116, 127. Avram's sister, Klara Katz, was deported from Egypt for her activism in August 1925. Ibid., 397.
- 88 European Department, Office of the Director General, "Note on the Strikes," 338.
- 89 Foreign Office, Minute on Residency Paper No. 9065/153, 13 March 1924, FO141/779/1, BNA, 341–345.
- 90 The party was estimated to have 1500–1800 members, with several branches across the country. Alexandros Dagkas, "Tempêtes sociales en Méditerranée orientale pendant les années 1920" [Social Storms in the Eastern Mediterranean in the 1920s], *Le mouvement social dans le Sud-Est européen pendant le XXe siècle: questions de classe, questions de culture* (Thessaloniki: Éditions épicaentre, 2008), 33.
- 91 "Qadiyyat al-Haraka al-Shuyuʿiyya" [The Communist Movement Case], *al-Ahram*, 13 March 1924.
- 92 For the class composition of Wafdist leadership see Deeb, *Party Politics in Egypt*; and ʿAsim al-Disuqi, *Kibar Mullak al-Arabi al-Ziraʿiyya wa-Dawruhum fi al-Mujtamaʿ al-Misri, 1914–1952* [Large Landowners and Their Role in Egyptian Society, 1914–1952] (Cairo: Dar al-Thaqafa al-Jadida, 1975).
- 93 Reasoning for the verdict pronounced on 6 October 1924, published in al-Saʿid, *Tarikh al-Haraka al-Ishtirakiyya*.
- 94 Mohammed Nuri El-Amin, "International Communism, the Egyptian Wafd Party and the Sudan," *British Society for Middle Eastern Studies Bulletin* 16, no. 1 (1989): 27–48.
- 95 Ibid.
- 96 Tamim al-Barghouthi, "The Case of Egypt: A National Liberation Movement and a Colonially Created Government" (PhD diss., Boston University, 2004).

- 97 The period in question was characterized by a power struggle in which the Wafd was repeatedly pressured by the British and the king out of government despite its recurrent electoral victory for the sake of more pliable and palace-backed cabinets formed by Ittihad, Liberal Constitutionalist and independent ministers. Non-Wafdist cabinets that were formed intermittently in the period in question were equally, if not more, averse to communism and affiliated labor organizations.
- 98 Gorman, "Confining Political Dissent," 161.
- 99 Joel Beinin, "Formation of the Egyptian Working Class," *MERIP Reports* 94 (1981). Ironically, many of the emerging "local bourgeoisie" were resident "foreigners." See Robert Tignor, "The Economic Activities of Foreigners in Egypt, 1920–1950: From Millet to Haute Bourgeoisie," *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 22, no. 3 (1980): 416–49.
- 100 Keown-Boyd to Furness, the Residency, 28 February 1924, FO141/779/2, BNA, 3.
- 101 Field-Marshal Viscount Allenby to Mr. MacDonald, "Egypt and Soudan", 5 April 1924, FO141/779/1, BNA, 351
- 102 Ginat, *A History of Egyptian Communism*, 73–95.
- 103 "Al-Tahqiq ma'a al-Shuyu'iyyin," [Interrogations of the Communists], *al-Ahram*, 7 March 1924.
- 104 "Qadiyyat al-Haraka al-Shuyu'iyya. Bayan min al-Misyu Rosenthal: al-Haraka al-Mudadda li-l-Shuyu'iyya" [The Communist Movement Case. A Statement from Monsieur Rosenthal: The Anti-Communist Movement], *al-Ahram*, 12 March 1924.
- 105 "Qadiyyat al-Haraka al-Shuyu'iyya" [The Communist Movement Case], *al-Ahram*, 24 March 1924.
- 106 "Nafy al-Misyu Rosenthal bi-Sabab Mabad'ihi al-Shuyu'iyya" [Deportation of Rosenthal Because of his Communist Principles], *al-Ahram*, 24 July 1924.
- 107 "Al-Shuyu'i al-Ta'ih," *Al-Ahram*, various issues in the period 28 August to 10 September 1924. Perhaps the heading was meant as a pun referencing the myth of "the wandering Jew."
- 108 R. M. Graves, "Note on Recent Labour Unrest in Egypt," FO141/779/2, BNA, 34–36.
- 109 "Al-Shuyu'iyya fi Misr: Tasrihat jadida li-ma'ali al-na'ib al-'umumi" [Communism in Egypt: New statements by his highness the General Prosecutor], *al-Ahram*, 20 March 1924.
- 110 "Nafy al-Misyu Rosenthal," [Deportation of Monsieur Rosenthal], *al-Ahram*, 24 July 1924.
- 111 "Qadaya al-Shuyu'iyyin" [The Communists' Cases], *al-Ahram*, 15 October 1924.
- 112 Keown-Boyd to Wiggan, the Residency, Intercepted correspondences between British and Egyptian Communists, November 1924–February 1925, 14 February 1925, FO141/779/1, BNA, 445–451. While the Residency and Foreign Office opposed the establishment of diplomatic and commercial relations between Egypt and the Soviet Union, Britain recognized the USSR in February 1924 and began to have a Soviet diplomatic agent in London.
- 113 Ginat, *A History of Egyptian Communism*, 120, 127, 402.
- 114 Examples include Robert Goldberg and Samuel Kirsohn. See "al-Shuyu'iyya fi Misr" [Communism in Egypt], *al-Ahram*, 19 March 1924. Robert Goldberg was deported to France. Ginat, *A History of Egyptian Communism*, 122.
- 115 For the role and hardline positions of Keown-Boyd in policing political activity in Egypt, see Saneki Nakaoka, "Keown-Boyd and the British Policy towards Egypt," *Orient* 12 (1976).
- 116 Mary Innes, "In Egyptian Service: The Role of British Officials in Egypt, 1911–1936" (PhD diss., University of Oxford, 1986), 261–262.
- 117 On British predominance of the Interior Ministry after 1922, see Bakr, *Al-Bulis al-Misri*.
- 118 Major Anson, "Communism in Egypt," 18 November 1929, File No. 268, FO 141/649/2, BNA, 6.
- 119 Office of the Director General, European Department, "The Communist Movement in Egypt," 22 June 1925. FO141/779/1, BNA, 511–513.

- 120 Ibid., 514.
- 121 Ginat, *A History of Egyptian Communism*, 151.
- 122 Special Section, Public Security, Ministry of Interior. No. 3083, No. 3143, 5 December 1931, FO 141/708/17, BNA.
- 123 Sir S. Hoare, "Deportation: Attitude of Egyptian Government in trying to force Captains of Soviet ships calling at Egyptian ports to take on board persons whom the Egyptian government wish to deport but who are not Soviet citizens," 15 October 1935, No. 737, FO 141/532/9, BNA; and Keown-Boyd to the Residency, 3 November 1935, FO 141/532/9, BNA.
- 124 Graves to The Residency, 21 September 1921, FO141/779/1, BNA, 564–566.
- 125 Anson to Graves, 20 September 1925, FO141/779/1, BNA, 567–568.
- 126 Ibid.
- 127 Residency to Home Office, 554–555.
- 128 Foreign Office to Residency in Cairo, 19 August 1924, FO141/779/1, BNA, 553–559.
- 129 "Al-Haraka al-Shuyu'iyya: Wujub al-Qada' 'alayha qabl Istifhaliha" [The Communist Movement: The Necessity of Eradicating It Before It Proliferates], *al-Ahram*, 25 February 1924.
- 130 "Al-Hukuma wa-l-Haraka al-Shuyu'iyya" [The Government and the Communist Movement], *al-Ahram*, 4 March 1924.
- 131 "Qadiyyat al-Haraka al-Shuyu'iyya" [The Communist Movement Case], *al-Ahram*, 10 March 1924.
- 132 "Al-'Isabat al-Ajnabiyya" [The Foreign Gangs], *al-Ahram*, 13 March 1923.
- 133 "Al-Lusus al-Ajanib fi Misr: al-Hukuma la Tastati' Ikhrajihim min al-Bilad" [Foreign Thieves in Egypt: The Government is Unable to Expel Them from the Country], *al-Ahram*, 4 May 1924.
- 134 Ibid.
- 135 "Al-Muhajirun wa-l-Amn al-'Amm fi al-Qutr al-Misri" [Migrants and Public Security in Egypt], *al-Ahram*, 8 August 1924.
- 136 "Al-Muhajirun: Ihsa' Fariq minhum Ittiqa' li-l-Sharr," [Migrants: Surveying them to Avoid their Evil], *al-Ahram*, 9 August 1924.
- 137 "Hawla Muhajiri al-Hijaz" [On the Migrants from Hijaz], *al-Ahram*, 14 October 1924.
- 138 Shamir, "The Evolution of Egyptian Nationality Laws", 35.
- 139 "Qadiyat Nafy Rosenthal: Mas'alat al-Jinsiyya al-Misriyya wa-Abna' Turkiyya al-Qadima" [Rosenthal's Deportation: The Issue of Egyptian Nationality and the Subjects of Old Turkey], *al-Ahram*, 2 August 1924.
- 140 Ibid.
- 141 *Journal Officiel*, numéro extraordinaire 23, 10 March 1929.
- 142 Shamir, "The Evolution of Egyptian Nationality Laws," 48.
- 143 Ibid., 46–59.
- 144 Ibid.
- 145 Sidqi's close ties to the local bourgeoisie, through the Federation of Industries of which he was a vice president, shaped government policies toward labor. Marius Deeb, "Labour and Politics in Egypt, 1919–1939," *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 10, no. 2 (May 1979), 203.
- 146 *Journal Officiel*, Numéro 65, 18 June 1931.
- 147 The Residency to Booth, 19 June 1931, File No. 886, FO 141/767/21, BNA.
- 148 Booth, Office of the Judicial Adviser, to Smart, the Residency, 25 June 1931, File No. 886, FO 141/767/21, BNA.
- 149 Graves to Smart, the Residency, June 22, 1931, File No. 886, FO 141/767/21, BNA.
- 150 Field-Marshal Viscount Allenby to Mr. MacDonald, "Egypt and Soudan", 5 April 1924, FO141/779/1, BNA, 16–17.
- 151 Graves to Smart, the Residency, June 22, 1931, File No. 886, FO 141/767/21, BNA.

- 152 Ibid.
- 153 *Journal Officiel*, Numéro 85, 24 August 1931; and Acting Director General of the European Department, Ministry of the Interior to the Oriental Secretary, the Residency, 15 August 1931, File No. 887, FO141/767/22, BNA. For an account of the activism of Charlotte Rosenthal and her journey to the USSR, see Masha Kirasirova, “An Egyptian Communist Family Romance: Revolution and Gender in the Transnational Life of Charlotte Rosenthal,” in *The Wider Arc of Revolution*, ed. Choi Chatterjee et al. (Bloomington, IN: Slavica Publishers, 2019), 309–36.
- 154 Extract from Minute by O.S., 15 June 1931, File No. 886, FO 141/767/21, BNA.
- 155 “Draft Law to Combat Communism,” File No. 886, FO 141/767/21, BNA.
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- 157 Ibid.
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- 159 Bimbashi Ahmed Mukhtar of the Special Section, “Note on Communism,” October 19, 1931, File No. 886, FO 141/767/21, BNA.
- 160 M. Travers Symons, *Britain and Egypt: The Rise of Egyptian Nationalism* (Southampton: The Camelot Press Limited, 1925), 273–274.